

Cyclic voltammetric and EPR spectral studies of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complexes in organo and organo-aqueous media

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The electrochemical behaviour of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species has been investigated in different organo (ethyl alcohol, DMSO, DMF and AN) and organo-aqueous media containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) and 0.2 M KCl/KBr, respectively. The cyclic voltammetric parameters are calculated. Both the complex species involve two redox steps. The first couple ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) involves a single electron, diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible electrode process, while the second step involves irreversible reduction of Cu^{I} -halide species to metallic copper. Also, the reduction potential for the first couple (E_{pc1}) becomes more positive and that of the second step (E_{pc2}) becomes more negative with increasing percentage of a given organic solvent, indicating that the copper(I)-halo species becomes stabilized with respect to copper(II)-halo species. The EPR parameters (g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and A_{\parallel}) for the frozen solution spectra of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in ethyl alcohol, DMSO, DMF and AN, each containing 0.1 M TBAP at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) are calculated and the results are discussed.

The effects of halide ion concentration and/or solvent in the formation of complex species and their stabilities have led to considerable interest in the chemistry of non-aqueous copper-halide solutions¹. In our earlier paper² we have investigated the electrochemical behaviour of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species in different concentrations of chloride and bromide ions in aqueous medium by means of cyclic voltammetry. In this paper we report a detailed electrochemical redox behaviour and EPR spectral properties of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species in different organo and organo-aqueous media containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) and 0.2 M KCl or KBr, respectively.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical behaviour of 1 mM $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 0.2 M KCl and 0.2 M KBr, respectively at various percentage of organo-aqueous (v/v) – 25%, 50% and 75%, each of ethylalcohol, dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetonitrile (AN) was investigated at glassy carbon electrode (GCE). The cyclic voltammetric data for the first ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) and second ($\text{Cu}^{+/0}$) redox steps for the systems studied are given in Tables 1 and 2. The representative cyclic voltammogram for $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 0.2 M KCl/75% DMSO-aqueous (v/v) medium at scan rate 25 mV s^{-1} is given in Fig. 1. The electrochemical behaviour of 3 mM $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 3 mM $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was also studied in ethyl alcohol, DMSO, DMF and AN, containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl-ammonium perchlorate

(TBAP) at Pt electrode and the electrochemical data are given in Tables 3 and 4, respectively.

A single cathodic peak (c_1) appears on the negative-going forward cycle in the potential range from +0.70 to -0.10 V vs SCE, with a directly associated reoxidation peak (a_1) in the reverse scan (Fig. 1). Controlled potential coulometry shows that this reduction process involves a single electron per molecule of Cu^{II} -halo complex species. Both the chloro- and bromo-copper(II) complex species exhibit a second reduction peak (c_2), attributed to $\text{Cu}^{+/0}$ redox change in the negative-going potential scan in the potential region +0.70 to -1.0 V vs SCE lacking a directly associated peak in the reverse scan because of the rapid demetallation following this second electron transfer. This is confirmed by the appearance of the characteristic anodic stripping peak (a_2) in the reverse scan due to the reoxidation of the electrodeposited metal to free Cu^{I} ions (Fig. 1).

Analysis of the cyclic voltammetric data for the first couple, $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ (c_1/a_1) with the scan rate ranging from 25 to 300 mV s^{-1} at different percentage of organo-aqueous (v/v) solvent for 1 mM $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}/0.2 \text{ M KCl}$ and 1 mM $\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}/0.2 \text{ M KBr}$ showed that the electrode process involves a diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible single-electron transfer^{3,4}. Further, the anodic to cathodic peak current ratio ($I_{\text{pa1}}/I_{\text{pc1}}$) is less than unity, clearly indicating that the electron transfer reaction is followed by a chemical reaction³ (EC mechanism). Similar observations have earlier

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O in 0.2 M KCl at different % of non-aqueous solvents (v/v) at $v = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

Solvent	Non-aqueous solvent % (v/v)	First step							Second step				
		E_{pc1} mV	E_{pa1} mV	I_{pc1} μA	I_{pa1} μA	E^{IV} mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}	E_{pc2} mV	E_{pa2} mV	I_{pc2} μA	I_{pa2}^{II} μA	$E_{pc1} - E_{pc2}$ mV
Water	0	+125	+200	13.0	10.0	+162	75	0.77	-330	-105	15.2	45.0	455
Ethyl alcohol	25	+155	+230	6.0	5.0	+192	75	0.84	-450	-110	5.0	18.5	605
	50	+225	+305	4.8	4.0	+265	80	0.83	-465	-175	5.6	19.0	690
	75	+275	+380	4.5	4.0	+327	105	0.88	-540	-225	7.0	18.5	815
DMSO	25	+160	+245	7.0	5.5	+202	85	0.79	-425	-130	7.5	35.0	585
	50	+205	+285	5.5	4.8	+245	80	0.87	-535	-180	7.5	22.0	740
	75	+260	+375	5.2	4.5	+317	115	0.82	-750	-330	7.0	23.5	1010
DMF	25	+170	+270	10.5	9.2	+220	100	0.86	-420	-155	11.5	41.5	590
	50	+245	+330	10.0	9.0	+287	85	0.92	-615	-215	16.0	22.0	860
	75	+325	+415	8.5	7.5	+420	90	0.94	-620	-240	20.0	26.5	945
AN	25	+265	+360	7.0	5.2	+312	95	0.71	-470	-240	11.0	29.0	735
	50	+310	+440	6.5	5.0	+375	130	0.76	-575	-295	9.0	43.5	885
	75	+400	+490	3.5	3.0	+445	90	0.86	-640	-335	5.0	17.0	1040

^{II}Magnitude of peak current (I_{pa2}) is dependent on the switching potential.

been reported² for copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species in different concentrations of chloride and bromide ions in aqueous medium.

A perusal of Tables 1 and 2 clearly shows that peak potentials (I_{pc1}/E_{pa1}) are more positive while E_{pc2}/E_{pa2} are more negative as compared to the corresponding peak potentials in aqueous medium² for a given system. Also, the peak potentials (E_{pc1}/E_{pa1}) for the first couple (Cu^{2+/+}) be-

come progressively more positive while for the second step become more negative with increasing percentage of a given organic solvent, indicating that the copper(II)-halo complex species becomes destabilized with respect to Cu^I-halo complex species. Also, the separation between the peak potentials ($E_{pc1} - E_{pc2}$) increases while peak currents (I_{pc1} , I_{pa1}) decrease with increasing percentage of the organic solvent, as expected.

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 1 mM CuBr₂·H₂O in 0.2 M KBr at different % of non-aqueous solvents (v/v) at $v = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

Solvent	Non-aqueous solvent % (v/v)	First step							Second step				
		E_{pc1} mV	E_{pa1} mV	I_{pc1} μA	I_{pa1} μA	E^{IV} mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}	E_{pc2} mV	E_{pa2} mV	I_{pc2} μA	I_{pa2}^{II} μA	$E_{pc1} - E_{pc2}$ mV
Water	0	+140	+210	12.5	10.0	+175	70	0.80	-390	-90	14.0	50.0	530
Ethyl alcohol	25	+150	+285	11.2	8.0	+218	135	0.71	-500	-110	13.0	37.0	650
	50	+250	+335	8.5	7.5	+292	85	0.91	-535	-140	9.5	32.0	785
	75	+325	+415	8.2	8.0	+370	90	0.94	-570	-220	12.0	41.0	895
DMSO	25	+160	+255	11.0	8.0	+207	90	0.73	-540	-120	11.2	53.0	700
	50	+200	+305	7.5	6.5	+252	105	0.87	-600	-165	9.5	31.5	800
	75	+280	+365	5.5	5.6	+322	80	1.0	-725	-300	7.5	25.0	1000
DMF	25	+170	+260	11.0	11.0	+215	85	1.0	-480	-130	13.0	48.5	650
	50	+220	+315	9.5	8.5	+267	95	0.90	-620	-205	9.5	39.5	840
	75	+355	+430	8.5	8.0	+392	75	0.94	-920	-240	15.0	37.0	1275
AN	25	+290	+380	13.0	11.0	+335	90	0.85	-500	-230	19.0	59.0	790
	50	+360	+450	13.0	12.0	+405	90	0.92	-570	-285	21.0	53.0	930
	75	+425	+505	13.5	13.4	+465	80	1.0	-635	-325	24.0	59.0	1060

^{II}Magnitude of peak current (I_{pa2}) is dependent on the switching potential; $E^{IV} = 0.5 (E_{pc1} + E_{pa1})$.

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 3 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O in some non-aqueous solvents/0.1 M TBAP at Pt/GCE electrodes at $v = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

Solvent	E_{pc1} mV	E_{pa1} mV	I_{pc1} μA	I_{pa1} μA	E^{θ} mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}
Ethyl alcohol	+405 (+360)	+520 (+525)	6.2 (6.0)	6.2 (5.5)	+462 (+442)	115 (165)	1.0 (0.91)
DMSO	+195 (+245)	+395 (+385)	4.0 (3.0)	3.2 (3.0)	+295 (+315)	200 (140)	0.80 (1.0)
DMF	+280 (+425)	+540 (+510)	6.5 (5.0)	5.2 (5.0)	+410 (468)	260 (85)	0.80 (1.0)
AN	+435 (+490)	+600 (+605)	4.9 (7.25)	5.5 (6.5)	+518 (+552)	165 (115)	0.86 (0.89)

* Values in parenthesis are given for 1 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O/0.1 M TBAP at the GCE working electrode.

It is interesting to note that for CuCl₂·2H₂O the peak potentials (E_{pc1}/E_{pc2}) in 25% and 50% ethyl alcohol containing 0.2 M KCl (Table 1) are similar to those in aqueous² 0.5 M and 2.0 M KCl, respectively. However, in the case of CuBr₂·H₂O, the peak potentials (E_{pc1}/E_{pc2}) in 50% and 75% ethyl alcohol containing 0.2 M KBr (Table 2) are similar to those in aqueous² 1.5 and 3.0 M KBr, respectively.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 1 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O in 75% DMSO/0.2 M KCl at scan rate 25 mV s⁻¹.

A comparison of cathodic peak potentials, E_{pc1} at a given percentage of different organic solvents shows that both E_{pc1} and E^{θ} increase (i.e. become more positive) in the following order :

For CuCl₂·2H₂O/0.2 M KCl system :

- 25% : ethyl alcohol < DMSO < DMF < AN
- 50% : DMSO < ethyl alcohol < DMF < AN
- 75% : DMSO < ethyl alcohol < DMF < AN

For CuBr₂·H₂O/0.2 M KBr system :

- 25% : ethyl alcohol < DMSO < DMF < AN
- 50% : DMSO < DMF < ethyl alcohol < AN
- 75% : DMSO < ethyl alcohol < DMF < AN

It is to be noted that the peak potential (E_{pc1}) is most positive in a given organo solvent/0.1 M TBAP medium (Tables 3 and 4) as compared to those in aqueous² and organo-aqueous media (Tables 1 and 2) for a given system.

Fig. 2. Frozen solution X-band EPR spectrum of 3.0 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O in DMSO/0.1 M TBAP at 77 K.

Table 4. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 3 mM CuBr₂·H₂O in some non-aqueous solvents/0.1 M TBAP at Pt electrode at $v = 25 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

Solvent	E_{pc1} mV	E_{pa1} mV	I_{pc1} μA	I_{pa1} μA	E^{θ} mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}
Ethyl alcohol	+445	+575	6.5	7.0	+510	130	1.10
DMSO	+200	+335	3.65	3.2	+268	135	0.88
DMF	+395	+545	6.25	7.5	+470	150	1.20
AN	+525	+630	7.0	6.25	+577	105	0.89

Further, the reduction peak potential (E_{pc1}) is more positive, ΔE_p and peak current ratio (I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}) are larger at GCE than at Pt electrode in all organo solvents, exception being ethyl alcohol where opposite trend is observed. This indicates that the reduction is easier and the redox process is more reversible^{2,3} at GCE in a given organic solvent (DMSO, DMF and AN). Jecher and coworkers⁵ have also observed that the electrode process is affected by the electrode material (Hg/Pt electrode). In different solvents, the reduction potential, E_{pc1} , as well as E^{θ} increases (becomes more positive) in the following sequence :

At GCE : DMSO < ethyl alcohol < DMF < AN

At Pt electrode : DMSO < DMF < ethyl alcohol < AN

Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the reduction potential (E_{pc1}) and formal electrode potential (E^{θ}) for copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species shift negatively (i.e. become less positive) with increasing donicity^{6,7} (donor number) of the solvent (Tables 3 and 4), exception

being ethyl alcohol. Similar observations have earlier been reported^{8,9} for TPPFeX complexes.

Further, the peak current ratio (I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}) for Cu^{II}-bromo complex species is >1.0 in ethyl alcohol and DMF (Table 4), indicating that the electrogenerated Cu^I-bromo species is weakly adsorbed¹⁰ at the surface of the electrode.

Table 5. Cryogenic EPR spectral parameters for 3 mM solutions of cupric halides in some non-aqueous solvents/0.1 M TBAP

Solvent	CuCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O				CuBr ₂ ·H ₂ O			
	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	$ A_{\parallel} ^{Cu}$	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	$ A_{\parallel} ^{Cu}$
	$G (\times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1})$				$G (\times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1})$			
DMF	2.380	2.080	2.177	110 (123)	2.388	2.080	2.183	120 (134)
DMSO	2.402	2.080	2.188	110 (123)	2.402	2.080	2.188	110 (123)
AN	2.408	2.080	2.189	110 (123)	2.420	2.080	2.194	110 (123)
Ethyl alcohol	2.415	2.080	2.192	110 (123)	2.433	2.080	2.198	100 (114)

Frozen solution EPR spectral studies :

The frozen solution EPR spectra of 3 mM CuCl₂·2H₂O and CuBr₂·H₂O in ethyl alcohol, DMSO, DMF and AN, each containing 0.1 M TBAP were recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) (Fig. 2). The EPR spectral parameters are given in Table 5. It may be noted that the EPR spectral features of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species in DMSO, DMF, AN, and ethyl alcohol are similar. The EPR spectra are characterized by four small peaks in the g_{\parallel} region on the low field side and one intense g_{\perp} signal on the high field side. These spectra reflect the presence of nearly axially symmetric⁹ ($g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$) copper(II) complex species in solution. The g_{\perp} values are similar ($g_{\perp} = 2.080$) in all these solvents for both Cu^{II}-chloro and -bromo complex species (Table 5), while A_{\parallel} values are relatively smaller ($114\text{--}134 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). However, the g_{\parallel} values of copper(II)-chloro and -bromo complex species in these organic solvents increase in the order :

DMF < DMSO < AN < ethyl alcohol.

Experimental

CuCl₂·2H₂O, CuBr₂·H₂O, KCl and KBr used were of A.R. grade. Spectroscopic grade DMSO, DMF and AN were supplied by E. Merck, absolute alcohol by Bengal Chemicals and TBAP by Fluka were used as such. Freshly prepared solutions were used before recording the cyclic voltammograms. Experimental details have already been described in our earlier papers^{2,3}.

A Varian E-Line X-band spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating in 9.152–9.232 GHz range with 100 KHz modulation was used to record the EPR spectra. The g -values were calibrated with TCNE, tetracyanoethylene ($g = 2.0028$) sealed in a quartz capillary as an external standard and placed in the EPR cavity along side the sample. 3 mM solutions of CuCl₂·2H₂O, and CuBr₂·H₂O in DMF, DMSO, AN and ethyl alcohol, each containing 0.1 M TBAP were taken for recording the EPR spectra at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K). The frozen solutions were placed in a Varian liquid nitrogen Dewar flask for spectral measurements.

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